

Climate Change Impacts on Water Resources and Drinking Water Safety in Malawi: A Critical Review of Challenges, Implications, and Adaptive Strategies

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Abstract

Climate change poses significant threats to water resources worldwide, with particularly acute impacts in vulnerable regions like Sub-Saharan Africa. This review critically focusses on the effects of climate change on water resources and drinking water safety in Malawi, a landlocked country heavily reliant on surface and groundwater amid rising temperatures, erratic precipitation, and extreme weather events. Based on the global, regional, and local literature, such as the hydrological models and health research, this paper examines the changes in the precipitation patterns, evaporation and contamination threats that enhance the water scarcity and deterioration of the water quality. Key findings indicates that there are regional differences in floods and runoffs which could contribute to the mobilization of pollutants in the northern region of Malawi, whereas the southern parts of the country will have to face droughts and decreased water runoff that would greatly enhance the risk of water-borne diseases such as cholera and dysentery. Barriers such as limited infrastructure and low adaptive capacity are identified, alongside opportunities for resilience through integrated water resource management (IWRM), community-based adaptations, and resilient technologies like solar-powered systems. The review emphasizes on the need for localized policies, enhanced monitoring, and further research to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 6, emphasizing that without urgent action, over half of Malawi's population could face intensified water stress by 2050.

Keywords: *Climate change, water resources, drinking water safety, Malawi, Water scarcity, Water quality, integrated water resource management (IWRM), Hydrological variability, waterborne diseases, adaptive strategies.*

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Introduction

Climate change has had extreme impacts on global water resources over the past three decades ,altering hydrological cycles and threatening water security(Mbano et al., 2009). The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines climate change broadly as “any change in climate over time whether due to natural variability or as a result of human activity”(Pielke Jr, 2004). Climate change caused by human activity is impacting natural systems, increasing water-related risks, which leads to a need to address risks in the water sector broadly and globally, reviewing the paradigms that drive the development of water

resources (Rossi and Peres, 2023). Temperature increases and changes in rainfall patterns are two effects of climate change. The earth's surface temperature has increased by 0.6 ± 0.2 °C throughout the 20th century and 0.13 ± 0.07 °C per decade over the past 50 years (Singh et al., 2018). These changes, driven by rising greenhouse gas concentrations, affect precipitation patterns, evapotranspiration, and groundwater recharge, exacerbating water scarcity and quality degradation (Raneesh, 2014). In order to maintain life and perform fundamental daily tasks, water is necessary. Although water covers most of the Earth's surface, the freshwater required to sustain human activities is scarce (Biswas et al., 2025). Globally, an estimated 2.2 billion people lack access to safely managed drinking water (OECD, 2020), with climate change exacerbating this through altered hydrological cycles, increased evaporation, and extreme weather events (Organization and Fund, 2021). Projections indicate that by 2050, over half the world's population could face water scarcity (PatSnap Eureka, 2025), driven by a 20-30% increase in water demand amid changing climates (Koncagül et al., 2020).

Over the past 20 years, climate change has drawn global attention due to its intense impacts on water availability and quality. To address the issues caused by changing climates, adaptive measures must be developed. Rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns are major drivers of water stress, responsible for shifts in hydrological cycles worldwide (Kundzewicz, 2008). A country is labeled as water stressed when the population uses more than 20 percent of the nation's renewable water resources (Vorster, 2014), when water withdrawals exceed 40 percent such a country is considered severe water stressed (Vörösmarty et al., 2005; Ngoran, Dogah, & Xue, 2015). Many Sub Saharan African nations are experiencing water stress. In 2004, the International Dialogue on Water and Climate illustrated that water stress will surge significantly in Sub Saharan Africa (Ngoran, Dogah, & Xue, 2015). Approximately 25 percent of the present-day African population faces water stress, while 69 percent enjoys conditions of relative water abundance (Rijsberman, 2006), however abundance does not necessarily portrays availability of water (Ngoran, Dogah, & Xue, 2015). In Sub Saharan African countries, an estimated 1,100 million people depend on doubtful sources of drinking water, thus resulting in the death of 5 million people per annum (UNICEF & Organization, 2002; Ngoran, Dogah, & Xue, 2015).

Malawi, a country in Sub-Saharan Africa has not been spared the effects of climate change. The challenges posed by climate change have emerged as pressing issues in Malawi, a country significantly vulnerable to water-related crises. Malawi, is a landlocked nation covering an area of 118,500 km² out of which about 21% is water. However, the country's water system is increasingly jeopardized by climate change, driving alterations in precipitation patterns, temperature fluctuations, and the frequency of extreme weather events. Limited infrastructure and low adaptive capacity, exacerbated by poverty affecting over 50% of the population, hinder effective water management (Dinko and Bahati, 2023b). This review critically examines the impacts of climate change on Malawi's water resources and drinking water safety, exploring hydrological and health effects, identifying barriers such as inadequate infrastructure and governance gaps, and proposing adaptive strategies through integrated water resource management (IWRM) to foster resilience and support Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6).

Methods

The review summarizes peer-reviewed articles, institute reports (IPCC, UNICEF/WHO), and hydrological data to discuss the effects of climate change on water resources and drinking water safety, specifically on Malawi. Peer-reviewed journals in Google Scholar, Scopus, and Web of Science were primarily used as a source of literature, covering publications from 2000 to date. The inclusion criteria were prioritized to include studies that were addressing hydrological change, water quality, and health effects in Malawi or a similar Sub-Saharan African setting. Grey literature included reports of IPCC and UNICEF/WHO documents which gave global and regional background. To evaluate variability in

watersheds of Malawi, hydrological information of models (e.g., Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016) was synthesized. The review synthesizes both quantitative (projections of runoffs, temperature rises) and qualitative information and applying principles of integrated water resource management (IWRM) to assess problems, research gaps, and provide adaptive approaches to sustainable water management

Global Impacts of Climate Change on Water Resources

Globally, over 2 billion people lack access to safely managed drinking water, a figure projected to increase due to rising global temperatures and changing precipitation patterns (Organization & Fund, 2021; *Water* Editorial Office, 2025). Rising temperatures and heavy rainfall due to climate change elevate concentrations of dissolved organic matter, micro-pollutants, and pathogens, compromising water from source to tap. These pollutants increase the vulnerability of drinking water sources to contamination (Kundzewicz et al., 2008; Leveque et al., 2021). On the other hand, a rise in temperature will decrease the solubility of dissolved oxygen, especially when water levels decrease (Leveque, et al., 2021). This causes degradation of source water quality by promoting the release of nutrients and organic contaminants from sediments, especially when the pH is below 8. Thus, the eutrophication risk increases and the proliferation of cyanobacteria is promoted (Bates et al., 2008; Leveque, et al., 2021). In addition, warmer temperatures can also affect water quality in a number of ways, including increased pollution loads to water bodies, decreased stream and river flows. Reduced river flows will affect the dilution process between water and waste, potentially speeding up the organic nitrogen mineralization process in the soil (Salas et al., 2014). Climate change leads to deterioration of water quality in rivers. The potential increase in rainfall depth has a more significant impact on the river water quality than the increase in rainfall intensity (Astarai-Imani et al., 2012).

Compounding these direct impacts is a high degree of uncertainty in the predicted changes in rainfall and temperature over the coming decades (Thornton et al., 2014). According to estimates, greenhouse gas emissions have caused the average global temperature to rise by about 0.8 °C during the past century. In recent decades, variations in precipitation amounts have not been consistent due to the rise in global temperatures. Because of this, monsoon rainfall is more likely to occur in humid and sub-humid regions, while winter and summer rainfall will be lower in coastal and hyper-arid regions there by affecting water resources (Froelich and Daines, 2020). In some regions of the world, greater temperatures may lead to more precipitation because of the increased supply of moisture from evapotranspiration and evaporation processes. When paired with glacial meltwater, this additional precipitation can raise the region's rivers total water output and sediment carrying capacity. Global warming may cause glaciers to recede or even vanish, which would decrease the flow of rivers fed by glaciers during the dry season (Chakraborty et al., 2014).

Calculations with a global hydrological model that is driven by climate change scenarios of two climate models suggest that anthropogenic climate change may escalate (Döll, & Flörke, 2009), by the 2050s where by 16–19% of the global population may experience at least a 10% decrease in groundwater recharge, with highest vulnerabilities in North Africa, southwestern Africa, northeastern Brazil, and the central Andes (Döll, & Flörke, 2009). On the other hand, climate change disrupts natural variability, increasing the magnitude and recurrence of extreme floods and droughts in semi-arid regions like southern Africa and the western U.S (Cayan et al., 2017). In this context of uncertainty about the future climate, an adaptive risk management approach incorporating adaptation and mitigation measures is recommended (Leveque, et al., 2021).

Climate change introduces uncertainties to water quality and quantity in urban catchments (Delpla et al., 2009). Degradation of drinking water quality due to climate change poses significant health risks, particularly in rural and vulnerable communities. For instance, salinity intrusion, exacerbated by sea-level

rise and altered river flows, affects low-income nations, with a number of people lacking safe drinking water globally (Vineis et al., 2011). For example One-quarter of the global population live in coastal regions that have less than 10% of the global renewable water supply and are undergoing rapid population growth (Kundzewicz, et al., 2008). Saline intrusion due to excessive water withdrawals from aquifers is expected to be exacerbated by the effect of sea-level rise, leading to reduction of freshwater availability (Kundzewicz et al., 2007) In Bangladesh, salinity contributes to hypertension, a leading cause of cardiovascular illnesses risks for 20 million people (Rasheed et al., 2016).

The impact of climate change on surface water quality are summarized in Fig 1, which consider the effects (droughts and floods) of the two main factors (temperature and rainfalls) (Delpla, et al., 2009). These impacts depend on natural or man built environment, and the consequences can be different according to water body type such as rivers, lakes, dams, ponds, wetlands, and characteristics such as water residence times, size, shape, and depths (Delpla, et al., 2009). For streams, the main parameters affected are Dissolved Oxygen Matter and nutrients meanwhile pathogens and cyanobacteria/cyanotoxins are more related to lakes. In between, micro pollutants, inorganic or organic are also frequently affected (Delpla, et al., 2009).

Figure 1. Impacts of Climate Change on Water Resources and Drinking Water Quality
Source: Delpla et al. (2009)

Climate Change Impacts in Sub-Saharan Africa

Climate change is predicted to alter water availability in Sub Saharan Africa through increased temperatures and changes in precipitation (Paulos, et al., 2025). Water availability and water fetching times are dependent on freshwater availability, which is known to vary seasonally with precipitation and temperature (Paulos, et al., 2025). In Sub Saharan Africa, Temperature is positively associated with walk time across all time periods (Paulos, et al., 2025). The magnitude of effect also increases with the length of the time period; a 1°C increase in mean daily maximum temperature over the last 7 or 365 days is

associated with a 0.43 or 1.21 minute increase in walk time, respectively (Paulos et al., 2025). Climate change is predicted to increase annual average temperatures across Sub-Saharan Africa by as much as 4°C by 2100, cause decreases to annual precipitation by up to 20% in some areas, and increase the frequency of extreme weather events (Paulos et al., 2025).

Climate change leads to more frequent and intense weather events such as flooding and droughts, which can contaminate water sources and increase the prevalence of waterborne diseases like cholera, typhoid fever, schistosomiasis, and hepatitis A, which affect populations throughout Sub-Saharan Africa. Limited access to clean water, sanitation, and hygiene infrastructure constitute significant risk factors for such diseases (Veolia Institute, 2025). Extreme climate-related events exacerbate these risks (Veolia Institute, 2025). For example, flooding can lead to contaminated water sources, while droughts compromise water quantity and quality (Moore and Colwell, 2025). In addition, climate change aggravates groundwater contamination. Groundwater in regions like Ethiopia and Kenya often contains chemical contaminants such as fluoride, arsenic, nitrate, and salinity, which pose health risks. These contaminants are not regularly monitored, highlighting the need for improved water treatment infrastructure and equitable access to safe drinking water. Sustainable Development Goal target 6.1 will not be achieved without wider implementation of groundwater treatment, thus a shift is required in how water systems are designed and managed (Nowicki et al., 2023). Furthermore, climate change in Sub-Saharan Africa is severely affecting water access, compromising the health and safety of millions. Studies in the Nile Basin region show high levels of microbial contamination in drinking water sources, with significant presence of Total Coliforms, *E. coli*, *Salmonella* spp. and *Helicobacter pylori*. This contamination persists despite domestic water treatment efforts, indicating the need for improved water quality monitoring and management policies (Watti et al., 2025).

Climate change exacerbates water scarcity, affecting both the quantity and quality of available water. In regions like Iwo, Nigeria, household water consumption often exceeds supply, leading to significant water stress, confirming the likelihood of climate change effects (Ogunbode et al., 2025). This scarcity is compounded by inadequate infrastructure and inefficient water flow networks (Tularam and Hassan, 2016). Livestock systems face similar impacts, with reduced water availability affecting pastoralism (Bashiru and Oseni, 2025).

Specific Impacts in Malawi

The majority of Malawians depend on surface water for domestic, agricultural, and industrial purposes, directly linking their health and livelihoods to the availability and quality of these resources (Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016). This dependency is particularly critical given the country's high vulnerability to climate change, driven by limited adaptive capacities due to low HDI (0.477) and poverty, affecting over 50% of the population (Dinko and Bahati, 2023a). The impacts are already evident, since 1960 Malawi has experienced a 0.9–1°C temperature rise, due to climate change, with projections of 5°C by century's end, alongside erratic rainfall causing floods and droughts (Dinko and Bahati, 2023b), this intensified water stress. As of 2023, water stress affected large portions of the population, with only 59% having access to safely managed drinking water, a situation exacerbated by increasing temperature and declining rainfall. This trend aligns with larger climatic shifts across Southern Africa, which is projected to become hotter and drier per Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (Stocker, 2014). As illustrated in Figure 1, the percentage of the water-stressed population in Malawi rose from 12.7% to 17.5% between 1995 and 2019. For context, this increase, while significant, was less severe than in Kenya (14.8% to 33.2%) and Ghana (3.7% to 6.3%) over the same period.

Figure 2. Rising Prevalence of Water Stress in Ghana, Kenya, and Malawi (1995-2019)
Source: Stocker (2014)

According to literature, Climate change is expected to cause significant variability in precipitation across Malawi. Projections indicate that the northern region may experience increased rainfall, leading to higher water yields and potential flooding, while the southern region is likely to face reduced rainfall, increasing the risk of droughts. Increase in rainfall in northern region will lead to increased surface runoff which may lead to increased soil and nutrient loss in the north. The southern part of the country may face increased water stress in the midcentury (Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016).

The historical hydrological baseline for Malawi's major watersheds is summarized in Table 1, showing conditions in the 1990s. Future projections for the 2050s, detailed in Table 2, confirm this divergent pattern. Under multiple climate models, northern watersheds like Rukuru and South Rukuru are projected to see substantial increases in surface runoff and water yield, which could theoretically enhance water availability. Conversely, watersheds in the central and southern regions, such as Lilongwe, Shire, and Lake Chilwa, are projected to experience declines or only marginal increases. For instance, some models project a decrease of over 9% in water yield for the Lilongwe watershed, which would exacerbate existing water stress in the more densely populated south (Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016; Adhikari et al., 2015). This imbalance underscores the challenge of managing both future flood risk in the north and intensified water scarcity in the south.

Table 1. Summary of Hydrological Conditions (1990s) in Malawi

Watershed	Rainfall (mm)	Avg. Temp. (°C)	Max. Temp. (°C)	Surface Runoff (mm)	Water Yield (mm)
Rukuru	877	23.6	28.7	61	187
South Rukuru	766	20.8	26.9	28	114
Namitete	908	21.8	27.8	71	202
Lilongwe	901	20.2	26.1	97	200
Shire	867	22.3	27.3	195	274
Lake Chirwa	1077	22.2	27.9	690	725
Kaombe	1104	23.4	28.7	147	472

Source: Adhikari & Nejadhashemi (2016)

Table 2 .Projected Percent Change in Surface Runoff and Water Yield in the 2050s Compared to the 1990s over the Watersheds in Malawi

Watershed	Climate scenarios											
	CanESM2		CCSM4		CSIRO-MK3.6		IPSL-CM5A-LR		MPI-ESM-LR		MRI-CGCM3	
	Surface runoff	Water yield	Surface runoff	Water yield	Surface runoff	Water yield	Surface runoff	Water yield	Surface runoff	Water yield	Surface runoff	Water yield
Rukuru	174.6	102.6	83.2	50.1	42.8	24.6	154.4	94.2	68.6	39.6	56.0	34.8
South Rukuru	76.4	46.5	50.7	32.6	5.1	4.3	181.2	112.5	38.4	23.3	74.1	50.4
Namitete	22.4	14.0	27.7	19.6	-10.7	-10.0	112.0	85.5	18.1	12.7	32.4	26.2
Kaombe	19.7	11.6	22.1	14.6	-7.0	-7.5	85.2	56.2	14.6	9.2	26.3	18.9
Lilongwe	12.7	7.1	20.6	15.1	-9.2	-9.4	73.9	55.4	8.7	5.6	13.8	11.0
Shire	6.5	4.6	17.3	15.8	-4.3	-4.9	51.5	46.8	-2.2	-2.7	9.4	8.7
Lake Chilwa	0.0	-0.1	8.2	7.9	-7.8	-7.8	46.8	44.7	-4.9	-4.9	1.3	1.1

Source: Adhikari and Nejadhashemi (2016)

Beyond surface water resources, climate change also poses significant threats to Malawi's groundwater. One of the key uncertainties surrounding the impacts of climate change in Africa is the effect on the sustainability of rural water supplies. Many of these water supplies abstract from shallow groundwater (<50 m) and are the sole source of safe drinking water for rural populations (Ampimah, 2017). In Malawi, Groundwater is a critical source of drinking water, however it is also affected due to increased rainfall intensity which may lead to contamination of shallow groundwater sources, while droughts could reduce groundwater recharge, particularly in marginal areas (MacDonald et al., 2009)

Furthermore, the hydrological system of Lake Malawi, a critical national resource, is also highly sensitive to climate shifts. Another scholar assessed the sensitivity of the hydrological system of the Lake Malawi and Shire River basins to estimate potential impacts of future climate on key hydrologic variables (Mtilatila, 2023). It was concluded that the role of lake evaporation is essential for changes in lake level and lake outflow (Mtilatila, 2023). Note that, currently, lake evaporation clearly exceeds rainfall over the lake. Although the effects of projected future rainfall changes on lake level and outflow were slightly larger than the effects of temperature changes, the sensitivity analysis identified the particular role of lake evaporation for the hydrological system of Lake Malawi (Mtilatila, 2023). Evapotranspiration effects (temperature increases as a proxy) on Shire River discharge are not as high as for the lake surface area, and they might be seen as the inherited influence of outflow sensitivity from the lake (Mtilatila et al., 2020).

Discussion

Climate change impacts Malawi's water resources, exacerbating scarcity and contamination, particularly for vulnerable populations reliant on unprotected sources. Southern watersheds, such as Lake Chirwa and Kaombe, experience higher rainfall and runoff, increasing pollutant mobilization from agricultural and urban areas (Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016). This elevates waterborne disease risks like cholera and dysentery, contributing to approximately 8,800 annual deaths (Mills and Cumming, 2016). Northern areas, such as South Rukuru, face scarcity with lower water yields, compelling communities to use contaminated sources during droughts (Adhikari and Nejadhashemi, 2016). For drinking water, these changes threaten both availability and quality. Reduced yields and runoff, combined with population growth, could drop per capita water availability below critical thresholds, while rising temperatures and drier conditions further exacerbate the problem by increasing fetching times of water (Abedin et al., 2019). In rural areas, where 84% of the population relies on groundwater or surface water, seasonal shortages may force reliance on unsafe alternatives, raising health risks from waterborne diseases (Hinton et al.,

2023). Districts in the Southern region of Malawi are prone to floods amplified by climate variability, have historically destroyed WASH infrastructure worth millions, leading to contamination and outbreaks. The cumulative effect of these climate-change-induced pressures on water resources is a heightened risk to human health from waterborne diseases (Abedin et al., 2019). This causal pathway from climatic drivers to safe water scarcity and ultimately to public health impacts is summarized conceptually in Figure 7. Mitigation measures requires strategies like improved watershed management and resilient infrastructure which are essential for safeguarding drinking water security. In addition Regional disparities within Malawi necessitate tailored adaptation strategies, such as region-specific water treatment systems or enhanced monitoring during wet seasons

Figure 2. Impact of Climate Change on Water Security and Public Health
 Source: Abedin et al. (2019)

The interplay between climate variability and water quality is complex. Heavy rainfall events wash pollutants, including organic matter and pathogens, into surface waters, compromising drinking water safety (Okech et al., 2019). Warmer temperatures, averaging 20.2–24.0°C, promote algal blooms and accelerate chemical reactions, further degrading water quality (Khan et al., 2015). These conditions disproportionately affect rural and low-income communities with limited access to treated water, exacerbating health inequities.

Adaptive capacity remains a critical challenge. Malawi’s reliance on rain-fed agriculture and limited infrastructure amplify vulnerability (Parry, 2007). Resilient infrastructure, such as flood-resistant wells and piped water systems, could mitigate contamination risks, but implementation is hindered by

economic constraints and governance gaps(Chakraborty et al., 2014). Community-based approaches, like rainwater harvesting and local water committees, show promise but require scaling. Longitudinal studies are needed to assess the efficacy of these interventions and predict future climate impacts on water security. Strengthening infrastructure such as the construction of solar-powered water supply system can help to mitigate climate change impact. These systems are designed to be robust against extreme weather events. Traditional sources of water, such as hand-pump boreholes, have proven susceptible to damage during flooding, leaving communities without access to clean supplies. In contrast, solar-powered "reticulated" systems can withstand elevated climate stress while accessing deeper groundwater resources, ensuring clean water availability even during dry spells(Longwe et al., 2019). This technology not only enhances resiliency but also supports economic growth through job creation and improved health outcomes from better access to clean water. Adaptation measures, such as improved watershed management and resilient water infrastructure, are essential to ensure safe and sustainable drinking water access.

Ultimately,for water resources management to be effective in the face of climate change, it is essential to reduce the implementation gap through better coordination between levels of government, strengthening political will and increasing awareness and capacity building among both decision-makers and the public. Furthermore, understanding community perceptions of water scarcity and the risks associated with extreme climate events is essential to guide public policies and institutions focused on water security, in line with the principles of integrated water resource management(Hucke et al., 2024; Javadinejad et al., 2020)

Conclusion

In conclusion, this review demonstrates the profound risk of climate change to the Malawi water security and the health of the population. The connection between increasing temperatures, unpredictable precipitation, and unique north-south hydrological imbalances is initiating a vicious cycle of pollution in certain regions and water shortage in other regions of the country. Such changes have a profound impact on the rural people making health disparities worse by exposing them to waterborne illnesses like cholera.

The way forward requires a concerted shift of direction towards a proactive and adaptive governance. Malawi should focus on investing in climate-resilient infrastructure, including solar-powered water systems and flood-resistant wells, through increased watershed surveillance and community-based management. Policymakers should advocate evidence-based and regionally-specific interventions based on the tenets of Integrated Water Resource Management (IWRM). Furthermore it is critical to address the knowledge gap that is critical regarding the direct connections between climate-hydrological changes and health outcomes (Longitudinal research is the key to successful targeting of resources). This can be accomplished by harmonizing them with Sustainable Development Goal 6, where Malawi will be able to protect the equitable access to safe drinking water and ensure its population is not subjected to the increasing uncertainties of a changing climate. Finally, it is necessary to develop international cooperation in order to protect the Malawi water security of the future generations

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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